

Synthesis and characterization of SAPO-15 molecular sieve using hexamethylenetetramine template

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Silico aluminophosphate molecular sieve SAPO-15 was synthesized using hexamethylenetetramine template for the first time and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques such as XRD, SEM, TG/DTA, elemental analyses, FT-IR and ^{27}Al , ^{31}P and ^{29}Si MASNMR. The results were compared with AlPO_4 -15 molecular sieve of the same template. XRD and SEM show that the synthesized samples were highly crystalline. The structure is stable upto 250° . TG/DTA reveals the presence of charge compensated templates. FT-IR spectrum of SAPO-15 shows the similarity of the framework with AlPO_4 -15. ^{27}Al MASNMR reveals the presence of aluminium in octahedral environment. ^{31}P MASNMR shows the presence of environmentally distinct two tetrahedral phosphorous species. ^{29}Si MASNMR indicates the presence of dominant Si : [4Al] species along with small Si : [4Si], Si : [3Si : Al], Si : [2Si : 2Al] and Si : [Si : 3Al] species.

Synthesis of series of microporous aluminophosphates (AlPO_4 -*n*) was first reported by Flanigen and Grosel and Wilson *et al.*². Aluminophosphate molecular sieves are made up of a regular alternation of AlO_2^+ and PO_2^+ tetrahedra and an overall neutral framework, without ion exchange capacity or strong acidity. They can be imparted³⁻⁷ with protonic acidity by incorporation of lower valent metal ions in place of Al^{3+} in the framework (MeAPO, Me = Mg, Co, Zn, etc.), a tetravalent ion (especially Si^{4+}) in place of P^{5+} (SAPO) or a combination of these two substitutions (MeAPSO). As a result, SAPO molecular sieves can have acidities comparable to those of zeolites. Statistically, Si^{4+} substitution can occur for P^{5+} as well as Al^{3+} , either individually, or together as a pair⁸. However, most studies point to Si^{4+} ions substituting for P^{5+} and or a pair of P^{5+} and Al^{3+} cations. Therefore the resulting SAPOs possess Bronsted acidity due to bridging hydroxy groups (Si-OH-Al) as well as silicious islands or micro domains due to pairwise (Al^{3+} and P^{5+}) substitution forming silanol bonds (Si-O-Si).

The structure of AlPO_4 -15 consists of columns of Al-centered corner and edge-shared octahedra linked via PO_4 tetrahedra top provide channels approximately parallel to the *b* axis. The ammonium cations in the composition occupy these channels and are hydrogen bonded to framework oxygen atoms and water molecules⁹. The phosphate tetrahedra are only slight distorted, and the average P-O distances 1.53 (2) and 1.53(1) Å for P(1) and P(2) and angles $109(1)^\circ$ are similar to those reported for other dihydrated

aluminophosphates such as variscite and metavariscite. The Al-centered octahedra are significantly distorted. These distortions are more pronounced than those found for $\text{GaPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (GaPO_4 -14).

Wilson *et al.*⁴ have stated that in the absence of organic molecules no microporous aluminophosphates can be synthesized and to overcome the tendency of Al to be octahedrally co-ordinated in acid media, high synthesis temperatures are necessary¹⁰. There are some exceptions from this statements. This aluminophosphate, AlPO_4 -15 structure does not require organic additives to promote crystallization. It can be crystallized in presence of aqueous ammonia¹¹. Synthesis has been successful also in the presence of *t*- $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$, *i*- $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$, hexamethylenetetramine and diaminobutane templates¹²⁻¹⁴. However there is no report till to-date on synthesis of SAPO-15 using any of the templates.

In the present study, SAPO-15 was synthesized with hexamethylenetetramine as template and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques such as XRD, SEM, XRF analysis, TG/DTA, carbon and nitrogen analyses, FT-IR and ^{27}Al , ^{31}P and ^{28}Si MASNMR. AlPO_4 -15 synthesized using the same template was taken for comparison.

Results and discussion

The powder X-ray diffraction pattern in Fig. 1 shows that the products are very crystalline. The observed interplanar spacings for this sample are almost identical to

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of (a) AlPO_4 -15 and (b) SAPO-15.

the AlPO_4 -15 as in the literature^{9,14}. The relative thermal stability of framework structure was obtained by XRD of samples heated in air at temperature 250° , the solid phase transformed into AlPO_4 -tridymite. The elemental composition of the product is $\text{AlP}_{0.875}\text{Si}_{0.25}$ and for AlPO_4 -15 it was $\text{AlP}_{0.99}$. The size and morphology of the SAPO-15 crystals have been illustrated by the scanning electron micro-

graphs shown in Fig. 2. The image of SAPO-15 shows hexagonal shapes with $7\ \mu\text{m}$ particle size. However AlPO_4 -15 is flag shaped morphology with $5\ \mu\text{m}$ particle size.

Thermogravimetric analysis of AlPO_4 -15 shows that it undergoes weight loss in two stages 5.0% at 200° and 16.30% at 366° . The weight loss is due to the loss of water and entrapped template molecules. SAPO-15 losses -21.72% in three stages, 5.10% at 205.2° , 13.07% at 348.2° and 3.58% at 508.5° . The first endothermic stage weight loss is due to the loss of physisorbed water and template molecules and second endothermic loss is due to the loss of entrapped template molecules. The third stage exothermic weight loss is due to the oxidative decomposition of charge balanced template molecules. Carbon and nitrogen analyses indicate that AlPO_4 -15 consists of 1.58% C and 5.39% N and SAPO-15 1.46% C and 4.97% N. However, the carbon content should be higher than that of nitrogen as per the ratio present in hexamethylenetetramine template. So the possibility of decomposition of the template on heating to ammonia molecule is not forbidden.

The IR spectra of SAPO-15, show a sharp absorption band around $3600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to the stretching of the OH group attached to aluminium. Peaks in the 3485 – $3258\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ region are due to the stretching of two types of water, the sharp peak at $1632\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ is due to the bending mode of vibration of free water only¹⁴. The FT-IR spectra of SAPO-15 and AlPO_4 -15 in the framework region are similar. The different modes of tetrahedral linkages give bands at $1240(\text{sh})$, $1024(\text{vs})$, $891(\text{m})$, $669.3(\text{w})$, $613(\text{m})$, $590(\text{m})$,

Fig. 2. SEM photograph of (a) AlPO_4 -15 and (b) SAPO-15.

Fig. 3. ^{27}Al (a), ^{31}P (b) and ^{28}Si (c) MASNMR of SAPO-15 and ^{27}Al (d), ^{31}P (e) MASNMR spectrum of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-15}$.

516.9(w), 424.3(w) cm^{-1} . The bands can be assigned to asymmetric stretching, symmetric stretching, pore opening, double ring and bending vibrations of T-O-T linkages as described in earlier¹⁵. The bands in the region 1200–900 cm^{-1} may also contain bands due to Al-O-H bending modes of vibration.

The ^{27}Al MASNMR spectra of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-15}$, SAPO-15, as shown in Fig. 3, have single peak resonances around δ -7.62 indicate octahedral coordination¹⁶. An additional small peak appeared at 15 ppm is due to the spinning side bands. The two resonances observed in ^{31}P NMR spectra of this compound (Fig. 3) is attributed to tetrahedrally coordinated, crystallographically distinct phosphorous atoms¹⁷, P(1) and P(2). As noted earlier, the P(1) O_4 tetrahedron is more strongly hydrogen bonded than is P(2) O_4 . Thus P(1) with lesser electron density has a resonance at δ -13.54 while

P(2) has at δ -19.74. However, the peak corresponding to P(2) is split (-30 ppm)¹⁸, probably due to further distinction in the water environment around P(2) O_4 . ^{29}Si MASNMR results show that the silicon is present in Si : [4Al] (91.58 ppm), Si : [3Al : Si] (95.00 ppm), Si : [2Al : 2Si] (100.28 ppm), Si : [Al : 3Si] (104.09 ppm) and Si : [4Si] (109.74) environment. However the peak at 91.56 ppm is dominant. Which shows that most of the silicon is replacing mainly phosphorous atoms in the aluminophosphate framework.

Conclusion :

SAPO-15 was synthesized for the first time using hexamethylenetetramine template. XRD pattern shows that the synthesized samples were highly crystalline. SEM photographs show that the samples has uniform hexagonal mor-

phology with a particle-size of 7 μm . However, the AlPO_4 -15 morphology differs from SAPO-15. In TG/DTA analyses, SAPO-15 shows three stages of weight loss, one higher than AlPO_4 -15, due to the charge compensated templates. The carbon and nitrogen analyses indicate the possibility of presence of template decomposed ammonia in the as-synthesized samples. The FT-IR spectra in the framework region of both the samples were similar. The ^{27}Al line observed at $ca -7.62$ for SAPO-15 is attributed to octahedrally coordinated aluminium Al^{IV} and suggests the presence of an octahedral Al complex containing two water molecules in its coordination shell. ^{31}P MASNMR of the silico aluminophosphate shows two resonance, which are attributed to tetrahedrally coordinated crystallographically distinct phosphorous atoms. The second resonance split is probably due to further distinction in the water environment. This peak has been obtained on incorporation of silicon in to the aluminophosphate framework. The ^{29}Si MASNMR shows the presence of Si : [4Al], Si : [3Al : Si], Si : [2Al : 2Si], Si : [Al : 3Si] and Si : 4Si species. However the Si : [4Al] species are in dominant.

Experimental

Synthesis : A typical procedure to synthesis SAPO-15 is as follows. 5.75 g of orthophosphoric acid (85%, H_3PO_4 , s.d. fine, India) was diluted with 10 ml of distilled water. 3.58 g of pseudoboehmite (74.2%, Al_2O_3 , Vista Chemicals, U.S.A.) was added slowly to the solution. The mixture was stirred well. A thick white paste was formed and was aged for overnight at RT. 4.28 g of hexamethylene tetramine (HMT, 98%, Aldrich, U.S.A.) along with 10 ml of distilled water were added dropwise to the above paste. Then fumed silica (0.453 g, 99.5%, Sigma, U.S.A.) was added slowly and stirred well. The final gel with molar composition Al_2O_3 : P_2O_5 : 1.16 HMT : 0.3SiO_2 : $45\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was charged into a teflon lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized in an oven at 180° for 48 h. The final product was cooled and removed, washed several times with distilled water and dried at 110° for 24 h. The product was subjected to various physicochemical characterizations. Same way without silicon, AlPO_4 -15 was synthesized for comparison.

Characterization : The sample synthesized during the course of the work was analyzed for qualitative identification by X-ray powder diffraction (Rigaku, Model D/MAX III VC, Japan; Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5404 \text{ \AA}$; graphite crystal monochromator; computer controlled automated diffractometer). Chemical analysis was carried out by XRF using a Rigaku 3070 X-ray spectrometer. The morphology of the aluminophosphate synthesized was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM

5200). The framework region ($400\text{--}1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the synthesized aluminophosphates were analyzed using a Nicolet 60SXB FT-IR instrument in the diffuse reflectance mode using a 1 : 300 ratio of the sample to KBr mixture. Simultaneous TG/DTA analyses of the crystalline phases were performed on an automatic derivatograph (Setaram TG-DTA 92). The thermograms were recorded in flow of air with heating rate 10 K/min. MASNMR spectra were recorded in the solid state with a Broker DRX 500 spectrometer operating at a field of 11.7 Tesla. ^{27}Al spectra were recorded at a frequency of 130.3 MHz, with a pulse length of 2 μs and a spinning speed of 3–5 KHz. ^{31}P spectra were recorded at a frequency of 202.45 MHz with a pulse length of 1.5 μs and the recycle delay was 4 s. ^{29}Si NMR spectra were recorded at 99.3 MHz, 2 μs (45°) pulse width and repetition time of 2 s. Tetramethylsilane (for silicon), 1 M $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and 1 M H_3PO_4 solutions (for aluminium and phosphorous) were used as standards.

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